

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC AND NUTRITIONAL STATUS OF THE ELDERLY IN SELECTED URBAN COMMUNITIES IN KANO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study assessed the socio-demographic data and nutritional status of elderly individuals aged 60 years in selected urban and rural communities in the Tarauni and Dawakin Kudu local government areas of Kano state, Nigeria. Seventy-seven (77) respondents were randomly sampled out of 96 older adults in the study area. This study aimed to assess the nutritional status of the older elderly. The results obtained for demographic information showed that 40 (51.95%) were aged 60–70 years, 22 (28.57%) 71-80 and 15 (19.48%) are 81-90 years. The gender showed that 53 (68.83%) were male and 24 (31.17%) were female. 19 (24.69%) were married, 22 (28.57%) were widows/widowers, 27 (35.06%) lived in rural communities, 33 (42.86%) lived in urban communities, and 17 (22.08%) lived in semi-urban communities. 42 (54.55%) were from the Hausa ethnic group, 7 (9.09%) were Igbo, and 11 (14.28%) were Yoruba, with Islam as the major religion practiced. The results showed that 14 (18.18%) had tertiary education, 22 (28.58%) were secondary graduates, 12 (15.58%) had primary school certificates, and 29 (37.66%) had no formal education. Meanwhile, the results showed that 14 (18.18%) were employed, 25 (32.47%) were famers/artisans, 10 (12.99%) were traders/business owners, and 28

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(35.36%) were retirees. The results of the mini nutritional status of the elderly aged 60 years and above showed that 31 (40.26%) indicated a reduction in their food intake due to unavailability, 9 (11.16%) due to severe loss of appetite, 24 (31.16%) due to moderate loss of appetite, 13(26.89%) did not experience a decline in food intake. Results of weight loss among the elderly revealed that 5 (6.49%) experienced weight loss of >3kg (6.6lbs), 32 (41.56%) did not know their weight loss, while 23 (29.89%) lost between 1 and 3kg (2.2-6.6lbs) with 17(22.08%) had no weight loss. 7 (9.09%) 41 (53.25%): we're out of bed/chair but don't go far. In contrast, 10 (12.29%) went out freely and 19 (24.67%) experienced other forms of mobility. Table 2.0 reveals that 11 (14.29%) patients suffered psychological stress such as severe dementia and mild dementia. The results showed that 58 (75.32%) patients lived independently while 19 (24.68 %) lived in a nursing home/hospitalized during the study period. The results indicate that 19 (24.68 %) of the respondents took more than 3 prescribed drugs in a day, whereas 45 (58.44%) disagreed on taking more than 3 prescribed drugs a day. In conclusion, both government and non-governmental organizations should prioritize the awareness on the nutritional status of the elderly toward improving their health.

INTRODUCTION

There is an emerging shift in the paradigm of population aging worldwide. Globally, the older-adults population is projected to increase from an estimated 524 million in 2010 to 1.5 billion in 2050. The proportion of elderly persons between 2015 and 2050 is expected to almost double from 12 to 22.5 % (Ainembabazi *et al.*, 2024). In Japan, the proportion of the elderly, older than 60 years, rose from 7.1 % in 1970 to 26.3 % in 2015 (Bonfoh, *et al.*, 2022). In the United States, an estimated 17.3 % of the population in 2022 was 65 years and above. It was an increase from a few years back and is projected to rise by 22% in 2050 (Korhonen, 2024). This demographic shift in developed countries implies that older adults persons would be working longer, which is a positive development. However, it is not without its challenges as the older-adults person' years are associated with nutritional crises and lifestyle illness.

The population is on the increase, while nutrition and health risks increase with age (Pai, 2011). The leading chronic diseases affecting the older-adults population are related to nutrition. (Sadi *et al.*, 2025) reported that the elderly population has been somewhat neglected out of three vulnerable groups (pregnant women, infants, and the elderly) that face nutritional and public health threats. Vellas *et al.*, (2006) reported that malnutrition is very common among elderly people, predominantly in the frail or sick, and that poor nutritional status appears to be a major contributing factor of poor prognosis during illness in these individuals. One of the most challenging aspects of providing adequate nutrition for the older adults is determining their nutritional status. Shuremu *et al.* (2013) reported that this problem arises because aging affects many of the anthropometric, biochemical, and hematologic parameters used for assessing the nutritional status of the younger generation. Second, individuals age at different rates.

A similar trend is observed in developing countries. Shetty (2012) pointed out that by 2050, 80% of the 2 billion elderly population would come from developing nations, especially Asia. In Southeast and South Asia, the older-adults population is growing rapidly with diverse health and nutritional crises, as reported in both regions. The elderly population in the Southeast region was 9.8% in 2017 and is projected to increase by 20.3 % in 2050. The Southern region is projected to increase by 18.6% by 2060 (WHO, 2024). The elderly population in Sub-Saharan Africa is expected to grow more rapidly than the rest of the world (Seid and Babbel, 2022). The elderly population in Sub-Saharan Africa would almost double from slightly more than 30 million in 2005 to more than 67 million in 2030, and the growth in the population aging is not uniform across the region (Velkoff and Kowal, 2006). The variations in the older adults' populations among countries in the region could be due to their better health and nutritional status than the others (WHO, 2019; Olawumi *et al.*, 2021).

Although any age group could suffer from malnutrition in the Sub-Saharan region, it is common among the elderly population due to their fragile and health characteristics (Seid and Babbel, 2022). Poor nutritional intake can increase the risk of morbidity and death among elderly individuals. In the north-west, 25.3% of the elderly were reported to be malnourished, and 56.6% of the population are at risk of being malnourished (WHO, 2019).

The expansion in the elderly is a worldwide trend reflecting the prolongation in life expectancy owing to the demographic transition in frequent nations (Pai, 2011), which is attributed to lower mortality arising from the longer lifespan of people and enhancements in public services and clinical care leading to management of infectious diseases. The proportion of older adults is rising promptly around the world. The global elderly population is anticipated to grow from approximately 524 million in 2010 to approximately 1500 million in 2050, with a major rise in less developed countries. (WHO, 2011).

The number of elderly persons aged 60 years or over is expected to increase more than twice in 2050 and more than triple by 2100. Globally, an expected ascent from 962 million in 2017 to 2.1 billion by 2050 and 3.1 billion by 2100 (Olawumi *et al.*, 2021). Around the world, the increase in individuals aged 60 or more is faster than that among all younger age groups (Sadi *et al.*, 2025). Nutrition screening of the elderly is extremely complicated; the shortcomings of previously existing screening instruments do not make the problem any simpler (Elghazally and Saied, 2019).

The focus is to increase longevity of life by ensuring that older person are without morbidity by improving their health and nutritional status (Johansson, 2015). Adherence to nutritional guidance to improve diet is important as it positively impacts their health-related quality of life. Recent studies have pointed out that the expanding elderly population requires nutritionists and health care practitioners to deepen their commitment to understanding the challenges posed by this demographic shift (Volkert *et al.*, 2024). Despite the importance of the health and nutritional status of the older adults in Nigeria, there is a knowledge gap exists in the literature regarding Northwest, Nigeria. The aim of this study was to carry out a critical examination of the health and nutritional status of the older adults in Kano, Nigeria. Healthy aging is a priority of the global community as the graying population is rapidly increasing (Kaur *et al.*, 2019; Papadopoulou *et al.*, 2023). As the population ages, more attention should be given to the nutritional status of the elderly, especially because it plays a key role in the healthy years of the elderly as they age. According to the Pan American Helath organization (2021), the elderly who are healthy and independent are useful to their families and communities, and it is a myth to see them as people who only receive health and social benefits. Hence, this study aimed to provide data on the socio-demographic information and nutritional status of the older adults in selected urban and rural communities in Kano State, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study site

The study was conducted among older adults aged 60 years and above in the Dawakin Kudu local government area with 15 wards and the Tarauni local government area with 10 wards in Kano state.

Study design

The study design involved the use of random selection of the older adults residing in selected urban and rural communities in Kano, Nigeria. The selected elderly were interviewed using a closed-ended structured questionnaire to provide information on socio-demographic information, nutritional status, and dietary habits to assess the impact of aging on their nutritional status.

Population of the study

The sample size used for this study employed 77 selected elderly aged 60 years and above across the study area out of the total estimated number of ninety six (96) population in the selected urban (Tarauni LGA) and rural (Dawakin Kudu LGA), Kano State.

Sampling and sampling techniques

Sampling

Structured research questionnaires were administered to the respondents to gather data on their socio-demographic information, nutritional status, and age-related dietary habits. The questionnaire was administered to the respondents for data collection as recommended by the research advisor (2006), and descriptive statistics were used to determine the frequency and percentage.

Sample collection

Primary data were collected with the aid of a structured questionnaire using personal interviews. The secondary data focused on the knowledge and attitude of the respondents toward exclusive breastfeeding practices and the level of compliance following a method of (Olawumi *et al.*, 2021).

Sample techniques

A total of 77 respondents were randomly selected from a total population of 96 elderly people aged 60 years and above residing in Dawakin Kudu and Tarauni local government area, Kano state, for the purpose of this study using a simple random sampling technique as described by Yamane (1976) for their socio-demographic data, nutritional status, and dietary habits of the elderly as they advance in age.

$$n \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} = \frac{96}{1+96(0.05)^2} = 77$$

Where: n = sample size,

N = population size and

(e)² = (0.05)² = margin error

Data collection instrument

The data were gathered using a research questionnaire as the instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was self-constructed and administered to all selected respondents admitted during the period of this research as described by Creswell (2012). The data collection stage involved identifying and selecting individuals for this study and obtaining their permission to be involved in gathering information by administering the instrument, which entailed asking them questions on their socio-demographic and nutritional status toward old age.

Analytical Techniques

The data collected on the socio-demographic information and nutritional status of the older adults aged 60 years and above across the Dawakin Kudu Tarauni local government area, which comprises 25 wards, were as follows: The study was conducted with the aid of a structured questionnaire (Yamane, 1967). The study employed

descriptive statistics, such as means, frequencies, and percentages, to describe the outcome of the data generated following a previously described method (Olawumi *et al.*, 2021).

Inclusion criteria

All elderly individuals aged 60 years and above in the selected study area whose consent was approved and reside in the selected study area were included. Elderly individuals who were not willing to participate through the consent form and resided in the study area for less than 6 months were excluded from this study as data collection was based on the willingness of the respondents.

Ethical Considerations

The purpose of the study was explained to the participants prior to the commencement of the study as none was coerced or bribed to respond (Adepoju *et al.*, 2020; Olawumi *et al.*, 2021). Prior to commencement, ethical approval was obtained from the local government secretariat down to the ward heads for data collection.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-demographic information of the respondents

Table 1.0 shows that the respondents in this study are within the age range of 60 years and above, with 40 (51.95%) being between the ages of 60 and 70 years, 22 (28.57%) are within 70 - 80 years and the only 15(19.48%) exceeds 81 - 90 years. The results show that 53 (68.68%) are male and 24 (31.17%) are female. The marital status revealed that out of the total population of 77 respondents, 19 (24.68%) were married, 22 (28.57%) were widows/widowers, and 12 (15.58%) were living with family and adult offspring. Meanwhile, 24 (31.17%) were living with adult offspring without either of the partners. Table 1.0 shows the results of the respondents' residences: 27 (35.06%) lived in rural settlements, 33 (42.46%) lived in urban settlements, and 17 (22.08%) lived in demi-urban settlements. The results in Table 1.0 show that 10 (12.98%) stayed or lived in a location of the study for <1-3 years only. While, 15+19.48%) lived for 4-6 years, 22(29.87%) lived for 7- 9 years and the 29(37.67%) settled for a period above 10 years in the same place or location.

The results of ethnicity of the respondents revealed that the majority were Hausas with 42 (54.55%), 7 (9.09%) were Igbos, 11 (14.28%) were Yoruba's, and 17 (22.08%) were other ethnic groups across Nigeria living in the study location. The results of religious beliefs revealed that Islam is the dominant religion in the study area, with 62 (80.52%) and 15 (19.49%) Christians and no pagan.

The educational qualification of the elderly randomly selected and interviewed in this study revealed that only 14 (18.18%) obtained a tertiary education certificate, 22 (28.58%) obtained their SSCE certificate, and 12 (15.58%) stopped at first school living certificate i.e., primary school with 29 (%) does not have a formal education at all. The results show that 14 (18.18%) of the respondents were still employed, 25 (32.47%) were famers / artisans, 10 (12.99%) were traders / business men and women, and 28 (33.56%) were retirees.

Table 1.0: Socio-demographic information of the respondents

Category	Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
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Age	60–70	40	51.95
	71–80	22	28.57
	81–90	15	19.48
	91–100>	0	0.00
	Total	77	100
Gender	Male	53	68.83
	Female	24	31.17
	Total	77	100
Marital status	Married	19	24.68
	Widow / widower	22	28.57
	Living with family and adult offspring	12	15.58
	Living with adult offspring without a partner	24	31.17
	Total.	77	100
Location and settlement	Rural	27	35.06
	Urban	33	42.86
	Semi urban	17	22.08
	Total	77	100
Period of stay in the location	<1-3 years	10	12.98
	4–6 years	15	19.48
	7 - 9 yrs.	23	29.87
	10 >	29	37.67
	Total	77	100
Ethnicity	Hausa	42	54.55
	Igbo	7	9.09
	Yoruba	11	14.28
	Others	17	22.08
	Total	77	100
Religious	Islam	62	80.52
	Christianity	15	19.48
	Others	0	0.00
	Total	77	100
Educational qualification	Tertiary	14	18.18
	Secondary	22	28.58
	Primary	12	15.58
	Others/none	29	37.66
	Total	77	100
Occupation	Employed	14	18.18
	Farmer/artisan	25	32.47
	Trader/business	10	12.99

Retired	28	35.36
Total	77	100

Survey filed, 2025.

Nutritional status of the older adults

Table 2.0 presents the results of the mini-nutritional status of the older adults aged 60 years in selected urban and rural communities in the Dawakin Kudu and Tarauni local government areas of Kano State, Nigeria. The results obtained show that the nutritional status of the elderly was assessed out of a total of 77 modeling population and that 31 (40.26%) of the respondents indicated a reduction in their food intake due to unavailability of food intake, 9 (11.16%) declined due to severe loss of appetite, 24 (31.16%) were due to moderate loss of appetite and 13(26.89%) of the respondents did not experience a decline in their food intake. The results of weight loss among the elderly revealed that only 5 (6.49%) of the respondents experienced weight loss of >3kg (> 3kg, 6.6 lbs), 32 (41.56%) did not know their average weight loss during the period of this study (i.e., within 3 months prior to the data collection), 23 (29.89%) lost weight between 1 and 3 kg (2.2 - 6.6 lbs), and 17 (22.08%) had no weight loss due to their good eating habits.

The results presented in Table 2.0 show that only 7 (9.09%) of the respondents experienced bed- or chair-bound mobility out of the total 77 modeling population, while 41 (53.25%) were out of bed or chair but did not go out far or move around freely due to age in relation to their health, while 10 (12.29%) went out freely on their daily life activities, and 19 (24.67%) of the respondents experienced other forms of mobility.

Table 2.0 revealed that 11 (14.29%) of the respondents suffered from one form of psychological stress or the other in their age, 44 (57.14%) disagreed with any form of psychological stress, 4 (5.19%) experienced severe dementia, 12 (15.58%) experienced mild dementia, and 46 (59%) experienced no psychological stress or problem at all in their old age with respect to neuropsychological stress occurring in old age during the period of this study.

Lastly, the results show that 58 (75.32%) individuals live independently and not in a nursing home or hospital due to aging, whereas 19 (24.68%) live in a nursing home or were hospitalized during the study period. The results indicate that 19 (24.68%) of the respondents took more than 3 prescribed drugs in a day, whereas 45 (58.44%) disagreed on taking more than 3 prescribed drugs a day.

Table 2.0: Nutritional Assessment of the Older Adults

Category	Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
In the past 3 months, has your food intake declined because of any of the following:	Food Unavailability	31	40.26
	Severe appetite loss	9	11.69
	Moderate appetite loss	24	31.16
	No appetite loss	13	16.89
	Total	77	100
What has been your weight loss during the last 3 months?	> 3 kg (6.6 lbs)	5	6.49
	Don't know	32	41.56
	1–3 kg (2.2–6.6 lbs)	23	29.87
	No weight loss	17	22.08
	Total	77	100
What type of mobility have you experienced?	Bed or chair bound	7	9.09
	Out of bed or chair but does not go out	41	53.25
	Goes out freely	10	12.99
	Others	19	24.67
	Total	77	100
Have you suffered any psychological stress in the last 3 months?	Yes	11	14.29
	No	44	57.14
	Don't know	22	28.57
	Total	77	100
What type of neuropsychological stress have you experienced in the last 3 months?	Severe Dementia or Depression	4	5.19
	Mild dementia	12	15.58
	No psychological problems	46	59.74
	Others	15	19.48
	Total	77	100
Do you work independently (not in a nursing home or hospital)?	Yes	58	75.32
	No	19	24.68

	Total	77	100
Do you take more than 3 prescribed drugs in a day?	Yes	19	24.68
	No	45	58.44
	Don't know	13	16.88
	Total	77	100
Do you experience pressure sores or skin ulcers?	Yes	12	15.58
	No	31	40.26
	Don't know	34	44.16
	Total	77	100

Survey filed, 2025

DISCUSSION

Several socio-demographic factors have been identified to be associated with the nutritional status of the elderly in low income countries like Nigeria. Of these, socio-demographic data is one of the indicators or an explanatory variables to good nutritional status among the elderly as reported by (WHO, 2019; Ajayi *et al.*, 2015). The present study assessed the socio-demographic characteristics and the nutritional status of the elderly in selected communities in Tarauni and Dawakin kudu local government area of Kano State. Socio-demographic characteristics is an aspects of the population such as age, gender, present occupation, residential area i.e. urban, semi urban or rural, estimated year living in a particular place, ethnicity, religion, educational background and profession or carrier etc. are part of the important factor that can be used in explaining differences in nutritional status (Olayiwola and Ketiku, 2006), are chronological age is an important factor in evaluating the nutrient intake and the elderly nutritional status. In the present study, almost half of the respondents were above 60 years i.e. falls between 60-68 years, less than one fifth were between 70-80 years, while others were 81 years and above. Age distribution of the respondents in the present study is in line with the findings of (Afolabi *et al.*, 2012) in a

similar study conducted among Yoruba elderly in Nigeria; (Adepoju and Coker, 2018) in a study conducted among the elderly residing in low income area of south west Nigeria and (Olayiwola and Ketiku, 2006), in a study conducted among elderly residing in Ilaro town, Ogun state, Nigeria. This finding conducted in two most busy and considered with high elderly activities indicates that few of the respondents were above 75 years old, which suggest that only few proportions of the elderly in the study area live above 80 years of age and female elderly were found to be older than male elderly but in few number, and the religious background of the study area doesn't permit men to visit homes for this kind of research which tends to lower the number of elderly female participation (Afolabi *et al.*, 2012). Also, this may be partly due to the poor survival capacities of this population entrenched in the extent of poverty and economic situation of the country as indicated by (Adepoju *et al.*, 2020). Also, majority of the selected elderly has no formal education with the estimated number of only 14(18.18) had their formal education up to tertiary level with majority without any form of formal education and small number were retirees and between 4 – 6 were still employed and the majority were engaged in petty trading, farming and other forms of lively hood despite the age bracket. The educational attainment, the occupational carrier of the respondents in the present study indicate that majority of them were of low socio-economic status. This finding corroborate with that of (Afolabi *et al.*, 2012) in a similar study conducted among the same group of people among Yoruba speaking state and the study conducted by (Olawumi *et al.*, 2022) among the community dwelling elderly in southern Lagos. The low socioeconomic status observed in this study will have a detrimental effect on their food intake and their overall wellbeing which reflects on their health condition as an individual who are aged and need more time to rest and maintain a healthy immune system (WO, 2019). At different stages of life, changes in body composition differ in both sex and these changes are reflected in body changes as we age. Advanced in age has been linked to various structural modification in skeletal system such as demineralization which affect the structure of the bone in so many ways like; reduction of the width of the vertebrae as well as the deformation of the long bones and inferior extremities (Agarwal *et al.*, 2013). Also, various physiological and nutritional changes are associated with aging and this are usually manifested by reduction in height and weight, body mass index, muscular mass loss, increase in fat mass and adipose tissue redistribution, with fat accumulation in the trunk and viscera as reported in a similar study conducted by (26). Furthermore, intake of energy and nutrients like; protein, fiber and fat were less than Recommended diets among both male and female respondents. The nutrient and energy intake of the elderly in the present study is in line with that of (Bonfoh *et al.*, 2022) in a research conducted among the same group of people in low income area of southwest Nigeria and Agarwalla *et al.*, 2015) in a study conducted in rural communities in Nigeria. This finding was opined by Bonfoh *et al.*, (2022) to be a general trend among elderly in Nigeria, also give credence to this. In the same vain, Intake of vitamin C, B complex and minerals like calcium, phosphorus, sodium, potassium and iron were found to be below RDA, which is also in agreement with the study conducted by (Agarwalla *et al.*, 2015). This can be linked to inadequate energy intake as opined by (29) and low intake of animal based food as indicated by (Agarwal *et al.*, 2013) Individuals' nutritional status is the outcome of multifaceted interaction of personal and environmental factors. In the present study, a significant association was observed between the nutritional statuses of the older adults, which is consistent with other studies (Bonfoh *et al.*, 2022). This gives credence to the general belief that functional dependency increases an individual's vulnerability to malnutrition, affects food intake, and increases dependency in performing essential activities such as cooking and shopping (Agarwal *et al.*, 2015).

Conclusion

This study investigates the socio-demographic and nutritional status of the older adults in selected communities in the Tarauni and Dawakin Kudu local government areas of Kano state. The nutritional status of the respondents was significantly associated with their socio-demographic data, which indicates that in old age without

establishing a fortress to support the family, the financial aspect will always be low, and physical activity was significantly associated with the age and present occupation of the respondents as well as the socio-demographic and economic characteristics such as age, educational attainment, and present occupation.

Functional policies and awareness are needed to improve the nutrition, health, and general well-being of the older adults in the study area. Efforts should also be initiated to help the older people adopt healthy lifestyle practices to maintain or improve their physical and nutritional status. Further research is recommended to authenticate the various functional evaluation tools or questionnaires to make them more culturally sensitive and reliable, thereby restraining the reporting bias.

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